

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

TO01000112-V5 Site monitoring plan

Authors: Juraj Franců, Petr Jirman, Vladimír Kolečka,
Miroslav Pereszlenyi, Aleš Havlín (CGS),
Jiří Gavor, Štěpán Káňa, Antonín Uher, Milan Pagáč (MND),
Anton Shchipanov (NORCE),
Petr Kolář, Zuzana Jechumtálová (IGF)
Naďa Rapantová (VŠB-TUO)

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1 INTRODUCTION

According to the Act No. 85/2012 Sb. on storage of carbon dioxide in natural underground geological formations, storage site monitoring is one of the main obligations of a storage site operator, both during site operations and after site closure. Monitoring has to be based on a comprehensive monitoring plan fully satisfying the requirements of the Act.

The Site monitoring plan was prepared despite the planned CO₂ to be injected into the Zar-3 storage complex is below the limit of 100,000 t and thus this pilot project is not subject to the provisions of the Act due to the given amount.

The aim of this Site monitoring plan is to (1) test the prescribed methodology for a specific geological location and, at the same time, to (2) prepare an important document for the application for a CO₂ injection permit that will need to be submitted before any CO₂ can be injected into the reservoir.

The Site monitoring plan involves the international CCS project guidelines (such as the Guidance Documents to the European CCS Directive) and other international literature as an input. Other key inputs include the reports of R7.4 Applicability matrix of monitoring methods at Zar-3 (Kolejka et al., 2021), R7.8 Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ plume monitoring (Pervzner & Gurevich, 2023), R7.3 Data set and Technical Report on atmogeochemical monitoring results (Jirman et al., 2023), R7.7 Data set and report with results of seismic monitoring (Jechumtálová & Kolář, 2024), R7.6 Data set and report with results of reservoir containment monitoring (Shchipanov & Pagáč, 2024) and R7.5 Data set and report with results of shallow groundwater monitoring (Havlín et al., 2023) of the CO₂-SPICER project.

The Site monitoring plan was prepared in a way ensuring full compliance with applicable legislation as well as the recommendations set out in the Guidance Documents, including the specification of individual monitoring stages, monitoring methods and their respective scopes, parameters, survey frequencies, etc.

1.1 Objectives of the monitoring

The monitoring plan has the objectives of both verifying the performance of injection operations and controlling environmental impacts and risks.

The monitoring is subdivided in time into 3 phases. The first phase consists of baseline monitoring that is carried out prior the injection of CO₂ into the storage complex. The baseline monitoring serves to obtain a comprehensive picture of the background = natural geological and environmental conditions of the storage site. Next monitoring phase is the operational one, which takes place during the actual CO₂ injection and storage process. The monitoring plan shall be updated accordingly based on this monitoring phase. The last phase is the post-closure monitoring and is performed to prove the modelled behavior of CO₂ and to confirm that the CO₂ remains stored permanently with no leakage to the surface.

1.2 Pilot locality ZAR-3

The target geological structure of CO₂-SPICER project “Zar-3” is an oil and gas field located in the SE part of the Czech Republic. The site operator, MND company, is one of the key partners of CO₂-SPICER project.

The Zar-3 field was discovered in 2001. This relatively “young age” of the field, together with the ongoing oil and gas production provide many advantages. Currently, the field is considered as “mature” with a declining production trend. The field was identified as a suitable candidate for the pilot project of geological storage of CO₂.

The area of interest comprises a total of 22 deep wells (Fig. 1-1, Tab. 1-1); 14 wells penetrated the reservoir itself, 4 are the side-tracks. Most of the wells are oriented or horizontal. The reservoir structure is situated in an erosional relic of fractured Jurassic dolomites (Fig. 1-2) on the SE margin of the Bohemian Massif, sealed by Upper Jurassic and Eocene strata overlain by the Carpathian Flysch fold-and-thrust belt. NNW-SSE cross-section through selected wells is shown in Fig. 1-2.

Most of the land above the oil and gas field is used for the agricultural purposes as arable land or minor vineyards. Orchards and gardens are located on more inclined areas to the north. Northernmost part of the area is covered by forests. Three settlements are located in the area: Uhřice, Zarošice and Archlebov (Fig. 1-1).

Fig. 1-1: Location of the Zar-3 field with well-heads and cross-section shown in Fig. 1-2.

Fig. 1-2: NNW-SSE regional section through the projected UH11, ZA6A, ZA6, ZA3, ZA4A and ZA7 wells.

Tab. 1-1: List of the exploration and production wells in the Zar-3 area.

Well (UWI)	ID GDO* (no.)	X (S42A)	Y (S42A)	Z (m**)	Measured depth (m)	Drilled (year)	Abandoned (year / comment)
UH3	461118	3644935.55	5437288.21	287.10	2595	1977	1978
UH5	462224	3646632.10	5437377.55	257.85	2050	1978	1978
UH6	461157	3646023.94	5438986.92	366.07	1420	1978	1983
UH9	461159	3642601.79	5436106.40	219.75	2800	1985	1997
UH10	461160	3643385.05	5435389.36	200.43	2911	1982	2003
UH11	461161	3643880.47	5438113.37	226.66	1711	1980	1981
UH12	461162	3645667.50	5439382.03	385.91	1500	1979	1980
UH16	461156	3643072.54	5436774.24	274.88	2800	1986	1991
ZA1	461214	3643548.20	5437234.93	220.76	2867	1965	1968
ZA3	645193	3644202.09	5437240.90	219.28	1923	2001	well in operation
ZA4	643952	3644197.83	5437256.52	219.25	1901	2002	unusable section abandoned
ZA4A	643954	3644197.83	5437256.52	219.25	1995	2002	well in operation
ZA5H	655774	3644044.68	5437843.83	247.80	2860	2003	well in operation
ZA6	655775	3644047.76	5437830.11	247.84	2020	2003	unusable section abandoned
ZA6A	655776	3644047.76	5437830.11	247.84	2032	2003	well in operation
ZA7	661637	3644204.31	5437233.33	219.26	2120	2003	well in operation
ZA8AH	731461	3644017.55	5437816.46	248.11	2440	2014	well in operation
ZA8H	730845	3644017.55	5437816.46	248.11	2347	2014	unusable section abandoned
ZA9AH	663046	3644206.44	5437225.53	218.64	2475	2004	well in operation
ZA9H	663047	3644206.44	5437225.53	218.64	1920	2004	unusable section abandoned
ZA12	-	3644028.16	5437818.91	247.47	2030	2017	2018
ZA14H	687067	3644207.92	5437219.66	219.27	2255	2008	well in operation

* ID GDO = ID of geologically documented object in on-line map application of Borehole surveys

** Z coordinates are given in meters above the Baltic Sea level after adjustment.

2 LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK AND RELATED GUIDELINES

The monitoring requirements for CO₂ storage sites are set by the Article 13 of the Directive 2009/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the geological storage of carbon dioxide¹ and amending Council Directive 85/337/EEC, European Parliament and Council Directives 2000/60/EC, 2001/80/EC, 2004/35/EC, 2006/12/EC, 2008/1/EC and Regulation EC No 1013/2006 (hereinafter referred to as the EU CCS Directive) as well as Section (§) 9 of the Czech Act No. 85/2012 Sb., on the carbon dioxide storage into the natural rock structures² (hereinafter referred to as the Storage Act) that represents the transposition of the EU CCS Directive in the Czech national jurisdiction.

According to the Storage Act, Section (§) 9:

(1) The operator carries out monitoring of the injection facilities, the storage complex, and where appropriate the surrounding environment for the purpose of:

a) comparison between the actual behavior of carbon dioxide and formation water in the storage site, with the behavior assumed in the final report prepared in accordance with another legal regulation (i.e. the Czech Geological Act No. 62/1988 Sb., as amended³),

b) detecting significant irregularities,

c) detecting migration of carbon dioxide,

d) detecting potential leakage of carbon dioxide and its volume,

e) detecting significant adverse effects on the surrounding environment, including in particular on drinking water, on human populations, or on users of the surrounding biosphere,

f) assessing the effectiveness of any corrective measures,

g) updating the assessment of the safety and integrity of the storage complex in the short and long term, including the assessment of whether the stored carbon dioxide will be completely and permanently contained.

(2) The monitoring shall be based on a monitoring plan designed by the operator pursuant to the requirements laid down in the Annex to this Act.

(3) The plan shall be updated at least once every five years to take account of changes to the assessed risk of leakage, changes to the assessed risks to the environment and human health, new scientific knowledge, and improvements in best available technology. Updated plans shall be re-submitted for approval to the District Mining Authority.

(4) Monitoring pursuant to this Act does not affect the obligations to determine, report and verify the amount of greenhouse gas emissions pursuant to another legal regulation

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32009L0031>

² <https://aplikace.mvcr.cz/sbirka-zakonu/ViewFile.aspx?type=z&id=24080>

³ [https://www.mzp.cz/www/platnalegislativa.nsf/d79c09c54250df0dc1256e8900296e32/d058aefaaee5dfdc1257015003636e6/\\$FILE/z%20C3%A1kon%20C4%8D.%2062_1988%20Sb..pdf](https://www.mzp.cz/www/platnalegislativa.nsf/d79c09c54250df0dc1256e8900296e32/d058aefaaee5dfdc1257015003636e6/$FILE/z%20C3%A1kon%20C4%8D.%2062_1988%20Sb..pdf)

(i.e. Act No. 85/2012 Sb., on the conditions for trading in greenhouse gas emission allowances⁴, the Czech transposition of the EU ETS Directive).

Monitoring technologies and monitoring plan are handled by Annex II to the EU CCS Directive (Criteria for establishing and updating the monitoring plan referred to in Article 13 and for post-closure monitoring) as well as Annex to the Storage Act (Criteria for establishing and updating the plan of monitoring and for post-closure monitoring).

According to the Annex to the Storage Act:

The monitoring plan shall be established based on the risk assessment analysis carried out according to point 3 of the Annex to the Geological Act and shall be updated with the purpose of meeting the monitoring requirements laid out in Section (§) 9 using the following criteria:

I Establishing and updating the monitoring plan

1. Establishing the monitoring plan

1.1. The monitoring plan shall provide details of the monitoring to be deployed at the main stages of the project, including baseline, operational and post-closure monitoring. The following shall be specified for each phase:

- a) monitored parameters,
- b) monitoring technology employed and justification for technology choice,
- c) monitoring locations and spatial sampling rationale,
- d) frequency of application and temporal sampling rationale.

1.2. The parameters to be monitored shall be set to fulfil the purposes of monitoring. However, the plan shall in any case include continuous or intermittent monitoring of the following items:

- a) fugitive emissions of carbon dioxide at the injection facility,
- b) carbon dioxide volumetric flow at injection wellheads,
- c) carbon dioxide pressure and temperature at injection wellheads to determine mass flow,
- d) chemical analysis of the injected material,
- e) reservoir temperature and pressure to determine carbon dioxide phase behavior and state.

1.3. The choice of monitoring technology shall be based on best practice available at the time of design. The following options shall be considered and used as appropriate:

- a) technologies that can detect the presence, location and migration paths of carbon dioxide in the subsurface and at the surface,
- b) technologies that provide information about pressure-volume behavior and areal and vertical distribution of carbon dioxide plume to refine numerical 3D simulation using

⁴

https://www.mzp.cz/www/platnalegislativa.nsf/29324B60A8C6D324C1256F86002E6B7D/%24file/383_2012.pdf

the 3D model of the natural rock storage formation established pursuant to the Geological Act and its Annex,

c) technologies that can provide a wide areal spread in order to capture information on any previously undetected potential leakage pathways across the areal dimensions of the complete storage complex and beyond, in the event of significant irregularities or migration of carbon dioxide out of the storage complex.

2. Updating the monitoring plan

The data collected from the monitoring shall be collated and interpreted. The observed results shall be compared with the behavior predicted in dynamic simulations of the 3D pressure-volume and saturation behavior undertaken in the context of the security characterization pursuant to the Geological Act and its Annex (point 3).

Where there is a significant deviation between the observed and the predicted behavior, the 3D model shall be recalibrated to reflect the observed behavior. The recalibration shall be based on the data observations from the monitoring plan, and, where necessary to provide confidence in the recalibration assumptions, additional data shall be obtained.

Points 2 (Assessment of the planned storage complex by means of a 3D static geological model) and 3 (Characterization of the storage dynamic behavior, sensitivity characterization, risk assessment) of the Annex to the Geological Act shall be repeated using the recalibrated 3D model(s) so as to generate new hazard scenarios and flux rates and to revise and update the risk assessment.

Where new sources, pathways and flux rates of carbon dioxide or observed significant deviations from previous assessments are identified as a result of history matching and model recalibration, the monitoring plan shall be updated accordingly.

II Post-closure monitoring

Post-closure monitoring shall be based on the information collected and modelled during the implementation of the monitoring plan as defined in Section (§) 9 of the Storage Act and in point 2 of the Annex to the Storage Act (on updating the monitoring plan). It shall serve in particular to provide information required for the transfer of responsibility to the competent authority as defined in Section (§) 13 of the Storage Act.

It is obvious that the Storage Act as well as the EU CCS Directive and their Annexes define parameters to be monitored directly, while monitoring technologies (methods, techniques) are defined indirectly as technologies that "...shall be based on best practice...". For more information concerning the examples of "based on best practise" for the Zar-3, see report R7.4 Applicability matrix of monitoring methods at Zar-3 (Kolejka et al. 2023).

2.1 IEAGHG on-line monitoring selection tool

A specific, useful and user friendly guideline is the on-line monitoring selection tool named "Interactive Design of Monitoring Programs for the Geological Storage of CO₂"

(IEAGHG tool⁵), developed and designed by the British Geological Survey for the Greenhouse Gas program of the International Energy Agency (IEAGHG) under the CO₂ Capture & Storage Research Theme. This monitoring selection tool has been created to identify and prioritize techniques that could form part of a monitoring program during all stages from site characterization (pre-injection) to closure. These techniques are collated for different parameters to be monitored (monitoring aims) to find a “matrix of applicability”. Further description of the on-line monitoring selection tool is provided in R7.4 Applicability matrix of monitoring methods at Zar-3 (Kolejka et al. 2023).

The results of the IEAGHG on-line tool runs are shown in Fig. 2-1. They represent a matrix (table), showing the dependence between monitoring aims and monitoring techniques (tools). The cells of the matrix show the suitability of a monitoring technique for the selected aim expressed by numbers from 0 up to 4. The number 0 means “not applicable”, number 1 means “possibly applicable”, number 2 means “probably applicable”, number 3 means “definitely applicable” and number 4 means “strongly recommended”.

Tool	Rating %	Plume	Top-Seal	Overburden	Processes	Calibrate	Detect	Quantify	Seismicity	Wellbores
Downhole pressure/temperature	50	1.0	4.0	1.0	3.0	4.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	3.0
Geophysical logs	44	1.0	2.0	2.0	4.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0
Tracers	44	1.0	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	2.0	0.0	3.0
3D surface seismic	43	2.7	2.0	2.7	2.7	2.7	0.7	0.0	0.0	2.0
Multicomponent surface seismic	37	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.7	2.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.3
Deep fluid chemistry	24	0.7	1.3	1.3	2.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
2D surface seismic	20	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7
Borehole seismic	19	1.3	1.3	0.7	1.3	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7
Integrated tools: behind casing	14	0.3	0.7	0.3	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	1.0
Microseismic monitoring	12	0.7	1.0	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	1.3	0.7
Atmospheric gas concentration	10	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.0	0.0	1.3
Sonar bubble stream detection	9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	0.7	0.0	1.3
Above-zone pulse testing	8	0.0	0.7	1.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
Surface-atmospheric gas flux	8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	1.0
Soil gas concentrations	8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	0.3	0.0	1.3
Satellite interferometry / GPS	7	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0
Tiltmeters	6	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.7	0.0
Airborne spectral imaging	6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
Shallow subsurface geochemistry	5	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.3
Bubble stream chemistry	5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.3	0.0	0.3
Borehole gravimetry	4	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3
Seismic interferometry	4	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Fig. 2-1: Matrix of monitoring tools vs. monitoring aims – results of the IEAGHG tool for the Zar-3 CO₂ storage project monitoring. Results are shown for the pre-injection phase (but will be practically the same for all stages of the storage site lifecycle).

⁵ <https://ieaghg.org/ccs-resources/monitoring-selection-tool>

In general, the IEAGHG tool represents a very useful instrument for basic overview of applicability of various monitoring methods for various monitoring aims at a roughly defined storage site. Its main drawback is that it does not distinguish between various lithologies, especially between the clastic reservoirs and carbonates, where mainly the physical and chemical properties of reservoir rocks differ significantly.

2.2 US DOE "Best Practices"

Another valuable source of information about monitoring methods is the publication “Best Practices for: Monitoring, Verification, and Accounting (MVA) for Geologic Storage Projects” (hereinafter referred to as DOE Best Practices), presented by the National Energy Technology Laboratory of the US Department of Energy (DOE/NETL-2017/1847, 2017 revised edition)⁶. This guideline is based on the United States legislation. Existing regulations in the USA relevant to the geological storage of CO₂ are mainly represented by laws and regulations issued by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA); similarly to the European case, the US monitoring strategies are risk-based. Most of the methods and tools coincide with the European approach but some useful additions to the results obtained from the IEAGHG tool could be identified. For more information concerning the description of individual methods, visit the US DOE “Best Practices” website (<https://netl.doe.gov/node/5827>) or see the result R7.4 Applicability matrix of monitoring methods at Zar-3 (Kolejka et al. 2021).

3 BASELINE MONITORING

The baseline monitoring serves to obtain a comprehensive picture of the background, i.e. natural geological and environmental conditions of the storage site. This is crucial for further comparison with both the operational (during site operations) and post-closure monitoring results. During the CO₂-SPICER project, the (1) Atmogeochemical, (2) Seismological and (3) Shallow groundwater monitoring were performed to identify the baseline. These methods and results are briefly introduced in this chapter accompanied by other relevant monitoring methods proposed for further baseline monitoring. For detail information concerning the mentioned baseline monitoring and other relevant methods, see reports R7.3 Data set and Technical Report on atmogeochemical monitoring results (Jirman et al., 2023), R7.4 Applicability matrix of monitoring methods at Zar-3 (Kolejka et al. 2021), R7.7 Data set and report with results of seismic monitoring (Jechumtálová & Kolář, 2024) and R7.5 Data set and report with results of shallow groundwater monitoring (Havlín et al., 2023).

3.1 Atmogeochemical monitoring

The atmogeochemical (referred to also as “soil gas”) monitoring belongs to the group of basic monitoring methods used for all terrestrial carbon dioxide storage sites. The main aim of the baseline atmogeochemical monitoring of the Zar-3 area was to evaluate the

⁶ <https://netl.doe.gov/node/5827>

compositional and quantitative spatial variability of the soil gas above the field as a basis to make it possible to identify potential soil gas anomalies related to the injection of CO₂ into the storage complex.

3.1.1 Methodology, monitoring campaigns and grid

Both periodical and continuous soil gas monitoring was performed. The periodical monitoring campaigns were based on 95 monitoring points (Fig. 3-1) using a portable Ecoprobe-5™ instrument (RS Dynamics) equipped with 4 independent infra-red detector channels for selective analyses of carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), total petroleum gases (TP = CH₄ – C₄H₁₀) and oxygen (O₂). In addition, ambient and downhole temperature, atmospheric pressure and pumping underpressure were registered. The soil gas composition was measured in each monitoring point at depth interval of 10-80 cm in holes drilled by a hand-drill (Fig. 3-2).

For the continuous monitoring, 5 monitoring points from the periodical monitoring grid (Figs. 3-1 and Fig. 3-2) were selected. The continuous monitoring was performed from June 2021 to October 2023 using permanent probes (Sapienza University of Rome and Idrogeosol s.r.l. company) with independent channels for CO₂ and CH₄. Hourly sampling interval was selected resulting in 24 measured values a day. The probes were buried 60-80 cm below the ground surface.

Fig. 3-1: Soil gas monitoring grid composed of 68 (labelled 1 - 68) + 27 (labelled 101 – 127) monitoring points for periodical monitoring and 5 permanent probes position for continuous monitoring included.

The soil gas baseline monitoring consisted of the following key steps:

- periodical field measurements 3 times a year from spring 2021 to summer-autumn 2023 in a grid of 95 monitoring points;
- continuous monitoring of CO₂ in soil gas at 5 monitoring points;
- cross check gas sample collection, their chromatographic lab analyses and based on that the final data correction (calibration);
- spatial analysis of the measured data using 2D contour mapping software;
- time-series analysis of the continuous measurement data.

Meteorological data, such as temperature (°C), relative humidity (%) and atmospheric pressure (hPa) were measured 1.5 m above the ground level by the Comet instrument calibrated by the publicly available meteorological data of the Czech Hydrometeorological Institute at the Brno – Tuřany airport located 23.5 km to the NW.

Fig. 3-2: Field soil gas measurement above the Zar-3 oil & gas field using Ecoprobe 5™ portable instrument (RS Dynamics, left and middle), permanent probe used for continuous soil gas monitoring is on the right.

3.1.2 Results of baseline atmogeochemical monitoring

During the baseline monitoring, a strong variability of the CO₂ content in soil gas was observed. The highest CO₂ content was measured in the summer-autumn seasons (9.67 %_{vol} in 2021, 6.42%_{vol} in 2022 and 6.28%_{vol} in 2023) with trends of spring increase and autumn decrease. The minimum CO₂ content in soil gas – typically below 0.5%_{vol} – was measured in winter campaigns. Similarities in the patterns of CO₂ in soil gas in the specific seasons were observed repeatedly (Fig. 3-3). Seasonal vegetation and microbiological activity were interpreted as the main controlling factor of CO₂ in soil gas. The rainfall total was identified as the second most important factor, followed by the land use. The atmospheric pressure showed an hourly-rated impact and was, in general, less important. Typical CO₂ values in soil-gas measured during the pre-injection phase are shown in Tab. 3-1. Those ranges are regarded as natural baseline.

Fig. 3-3: Average CO₂ content in soil gas in all 8 monitoring campaigns with similarities in CO₂ in the soil gas patterns marked by ellipses and arrows.

Tab. 3-1: CO₂ (%vol) in soil gas: min, max and averages.

Campaign	Min	Max	Average
1. spring 2021	0.07	9.09	1.51
2. summer-autumn 2021	0.06	9.67	2.47
3. winter 2021-2022	0.07	2.33	0.38
4. spring 2022	0.09	5.23	0.68
5. summer-autumn 2022	0.12	6.42	0.97
6. winter 2022-2023	0.04	1.52	0.25
7. spring 2023	0.09	5.61	1.42
8. summer-autumn 2023	0.30	6.28	1.54

Content of CO₂ in soil gas measured by permanent probes (Fig. 3-4) provided much more detailed data sets with trend of spring increase, summer maximum, autumn decrease and winter minimum observed during periodical monitoring. The measured annual maximum CO₂ content in soil gas was up to 9 %vol in summer 2021 but only up to 6 %vol in 2022 and 2023 (Fig. 3-4). The differences were interpreted as a result of vegetation and microbiological activity related to the weather conditions (Fig. 3-5). Strong increase in CO₂ in soil gas corresponded to the period after strong rainfalls. All the permanent probes

were placed in grasslands to exclude the potential effects of the land use and soil degassing. The differences among the trends measured by individual permanent probes (shown in colors in Fig. 3-4) were primarily caused by different soil types, water table level and vegetation in situ. The highest values (green line in Figs. 3-4 and 3-5) were observed in the valley floodplain with clayey low permeability on top of the soil profile. The lowest CO₂ values were observed on hilltops in more sandy soils.

Fig. 3-4: Time plot of CO₂ content in soil gas measured by permanent probes. For probe locations see Fig. 3-1. Blue pointers mark the timing of the periodical monitoring campaigns (usually 3-4 days).

Fig. 3-5: Time plot of the CO₂ content in soil gas measured by the permanent probes compared with the most important weather conditions factors.

Neither methane, nor the total petroleum gas were detected at significant levels during the baseline monitoring. The maximum CH₄ values in soil gas were < 0.5 %_{vol} and were not confirmed by repeated measurements at the same place, nor in different seasons. The methane was most probably of microbial origin.

The full baseline soil-gas composition dataset and maps were published in R7.3 Data set and Technical Report on atmogeochemical monitoring results (Jirman et al., 2023) and TO01000112-V3 Set of thematic maps of the CO₂ Zar-3 storage site (Kolejka et al., 2023).

3.2 Seismological monitoring

Seismological monitoring is another representative of the basic monitoring methods used for all CO₂ storage sites onshore. The 2011 EU Directive Implementation of Directive 2009/31/EC on the Geological Storage of Carbon Dioxide, Guidance Document 2, mentions the seismicity as one of the data for the characterization of the CO₂ storage site, while stressing the importance of knowing the seismicity for the “baseline characterization” based on known earthquake data. The importance of the knowledge of the induced seismicity is mentioned as well.

3.2.1 Methodology and monitoring network

The establishing of the seismologic monitoring baseline requires a long-term survey due to possible changes of the local stress regime, which may potentially lead to occurrence of induced seismic events. The natural seismicity was measured from August/September 2021 to August 2023. A monitoring network consisted of 5 monitoring stations (Fig. 3-6). The stations were equipped with 1 second sensor LE3D and Vistec Gaia digitizer, sampling rate 250 Hz. The stations operated in autonomous mode, in triggering regime, with daily status report; the data were stored on a SD-card and periodically collected. The internal time was synchronized by GPS. All the system was powered from a battery charged from a solar panel. All the devices (except for the antennas and solar panel) were closed in a protecting box (Fig. 3-7). To ensure good coupling condition, these boxes were fixed to the concrete plates of the drilling platforms. One station was situated close to a waterworks in an under-surface shelter.

A two-step procedure of seismograms interpretation was used: (1) by preliminary automatic picking and (2) by manual detailed interpretation of relevant seismograms. For the purposes of induced seismicity monitoring related to the Step-Rate test, a temporal seismic network composed of 11 stations equipped with ZATLAND 3C (Magseis Fairfield) independent instruments was set up (Fig. 3-6). The sampling rate was 250 Hz, and these small devices were buried to shallow depth at the observation points for several weeks. The instruments operated completely autonomously during the whole campaign.

Fig. 3-6: Map with positions of the permanent and temporal seismological monitoring networks in the Zar-3 area.

Fig. 3-7: Seismological monitoring at the Zar-3 site. Seismic monitoring station (left) powered by the solar panel (middle). Deployment of the temporal seismic network (right).

3.2.2 Results of baseline seismological monitoring

The baseline seismological monitoring at Zar-3 is based on both R7.7 Data set and report with results of seismic monitoring (Jechumtálová & Kolář, 2024) and Report of seismic and macroseismic observation in the vicinity of CO₂ storage site Žarošice (Jechumtálová & Kolář, 2021). Second mentioned summarized the historical events with known macroseismic effect and tectonic events which were recorded in the vicinity of the area. The estimated value of maximal acceleration in the area did not exceed 0.1 g in any case based on the data.

During the seismological monitoring in the area, neither natural nor induced seismic activity was identified directly at the site (Figs. 3-8 to 3-9). On the other hand, induced seismicity events were detected related to the mining areas near Ostrava and Lubin (Poland) (Fig. 3-8). The natural seismicity related to the Carpathian orogenic system was detected at the Austrian/Hungarian border or near Dobra Voda in Slovakia) as well as the strong teleseismic events (Figs. 3-8 and 3-9). All observed local events were assigned to the blasts in the quarries in the broader region, e.g. Lom Tasovice, Kamenolom Olbramovice, Lom Dolní Kounice, Lom Želešice, Kamenolom Vícenice, Lomy cementárny Mokrá, Kamenolom Luleč, Kamenolom Lhota Rapotina, Lom Předklášteří, Lom Mirošov, Lom Ořechov, Starý kameňolom Rohozník na Záhori, Kameňolom Trstín, Kameňolom Čachtice.

Fig. 3-8: Map with the locations of seismic events during the monitoring period with labelled anthropogenic or tectonic origin.

Prior to the Zar-3 monitoring, an exception of a single event was recorded in September 24th, 2003 in about 10 km distance – between villages of Lovčičky and Žarošice. The event depth was around 16 km (error is about 5 km) and local magnitude reached up to 0.9.⁷ For more details, see Data set and report with results of seismic monitoring (Jechumtálová & Kolář, 2024) and Report of seismic and macroseismic observation in the vicinity of CO₂ storage site Žarošice (Jechumtálová & Kolář, 2021).

Fig. 3-9: Map of the tectonic seismic events from the period of monitoring. Colors of the dots correspond to the calculated magnitudes.

The induced seismicity monitoring related to the Step Rate Test

The Step Rate Test (SRT) at Zar-7 was carried out on December 19th, 2023. It was designed to verify the reservoir absorption capacity for 3 different modes (170, 240, 310 l/min), each for 3 hours. A total of 135 m³ of working fluid was collected in the buffer tanks prior to the test. A cementing unit MPU - 400 with pressure and flow recording capability was used for the test. The recording from the downhole manometer shows only

⁷ Due to low number of that time operated stations, their distances from the event and weakness of the event, the location as well as the magnitude poses relatively high error.

a minimal increase in bearing pressure (approx. 0.15 MPa) even at the maximum liter of thrust.

During the SRT, very weak signal and an increased noise were measured by several of the closest seismic stations. A very weak event may have occurred, however, the signal-to-noise ratios were very low so that the hypothesis could not be verified. Therefore, no significant induced seismicity was interpreted during the SRT.

3.3 Shallow groundwater monitoring

Shallow groundwater monitoring is essential for both understanding the shallow groundwater regime on the site and establishing a baseline for subsequent monitoring of groundwater quality in later stages of site development. In order to establish the groundwater monitoring baseline, periodical water level surveys were carried out in the available hydrogeological and monitoring boreholes and water samples were collected.

3.3.1 Methodology and monitoring campaigns

For the shallow groundwater baseline monitoring, 19 monitoring points/objects were selected (Fig. 3-10), such as shallow wells, boreholes, water pumps and springs (Fig. 3-11). The shallow hydrogeological monitoring campaigns were performed in March, June, October and December each year and covered all seasons from 2021 to 2023. In 2023, the campaigns were performed in March and October only.

Following parameters were monitored: groundwater level (m), spring yield (l/s), electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), pH and water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$). The groundwater level was measured in five boreholes and five wells using the water-level indicator cable with ca. 1 cm accuracy. Spring yield was monitored at two localities. The spring yield was calculated from the time necessary to fill a container with a defined volume. The water conductivity is reported as the specific conductance, relative to the conductivity of pure water at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. An EC meter was used to measure water conductivity. For more information concerning the methodology used during the shallow groundwater baseline monitoring, see R7.5 Data set and report with results of shallow groundwater monitoring (Havlín et al., 2023) of this project.

Fig. 3-10: Position of 19 original groundwater monitoring points near the Zar-3 site. Access to 3 monitoring points (labelled as red dots) was not possible in 2022 and 2023.

Fig. 3-11: Shallow groundwater monitoring points/objects: shallow hydrogeological borehole (left), spring (middle) and water pump (right).

3.3.2 Results of Shallow groundwater baseline monitoring

The results of the individual measurements reflect the natural conditions in the area of interest, except for some minor deviations that can be attributed to inaccuracies of the measurements.

The water temperature (Fig. 3-12) and groundwater level (Fig. 3-13) reflect the effect of seasonal variations (temperature) and the depth of ground water flow. Water with deeper circulation has more stable temperature during different season of the year (and vice versa).

Fig. 3-12: Water temperature (°C) reflecting the seasonal temperature variations in the monitored objects.

Fig. 3-13: Groundwater level (m) in the monitored objects on the site.

The monitoring results indicate no observed anomalies in the water temperature, groundwater level, spring yield, electrical conductivity (Fig. 3-14) or pH (Fig. 3-15) in Zar-3 area as all measured data correspond to the expected natural conditions typical for wider region of the Zar-3.

Fig. 3-14: Water electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) results measured in the monitored objects on the Zar-3 site.

Fig. 3-15: pH values measured in the monitored objects on the Zar-3 site.

The full baseline shallow groundwater monitoring dataset including the shallow groundwater flow model was published in R7.5 Data set and report with results of shallow groundwater monitoring (Havlín et al., 2023) of this project. These data may be used as a baseline.

3.4 Other recommended monitoring methods

Using information gathered from the Guidance Document 2, the IEAGHG tool, the DOE Best Practices and the literature overview further discussed in Kolejka et al. (2021), recommendations can be drawn for selection of other baseline monitoring techniques and methods that will meet the conditions defined by legislation, in particular points 1.2. and 1.3. of the Annex to the Storage Act.

The IEAGHG on-line monitoring selection tool (see chapter 2. Legislative framework and related guidelines of this report) classifies another 2 methods – downhole

pressure/temperature monitoring and geophysical logging – with highest ranking, as “*strongly recommended*”. Tracers were identified as “*definitely applicable*” as well. These selected methods or technologies are briefly outlined in following subchapters. Text in italic indicates quotations from the IEAGHG tool or from the DOE Best Practices.

All other methods were classified by low rating; the reason might be the low amount of projected CO₂ injection into the Zar-3 storage complex. These low scores indicate a high level of uncertainty connected with the applicability of the assessed methods and tools. For more detail description of methods, visit the original website of IEAGHG on-line monitoring selection tool⁸ or see the R7.4 Applicability matrix of monitoring methods at Zar-3 (Kolejka et al. 2021).

3.4.1 Downhole pressure / temperature measurements

The Downhole pressure/temperature monitoring is strongly recommended as part of any CO₂ injection operation and seems to be one of the most important monitoring tool for the Zar-3 storage site as well. This technology is according to the IEAGHG tool characterized as: *Downhole instrumentation for measuring pressure and temperature is strongly recommended as part of any CO₂ injection operation. These parameters can be diagnostic of reservoir mechanical integrity, possible leakage from the reservoir or from a well and also of the physical properties of the injected CO₂. Baseline data will be useful, particularly when the site is an operational or depleted hydrocarbon reservoir.* The baseline data of pressure and temperature monitoring are available at MND for the period of field production history.

3.4.2 Geophysical logging

The IEAGHG tool characterizes the geophysical logging as: *One of the most common methods of evaluating downhole properties and conditions is by wireline logging, a mature technology that has been highly developed by the petroleum industry. Wireline logs are acquired by lowering geophysical instruments (tools) down the well and making a measurement profile of various physical properties along its length as the tools are pulled back out. The presence of CO₂ can change the physical properties of the borehole such that under favorable conditions these changes may be detected and measured by the well logging tools. Pre-injection surveys are important to assess baseline conditions and may also be useful for determining the most appropriate tools for CO₂ monitoring. A time lapse series of wireline logs, run both during and post-injection, can be used to monitor the behavior of the injected CO₂ and verify borehole integrity (CO₂ containment) across the caprock interval. The standard suite of 'open hole' downhole geophysical logs includes formation resistivity, neutron porosity, density, sonic velocity, gamma ray, self-potential and temperature. More specialized logging tools include various fracture identification, imaging tools and nuclear magnetic resonance tools.*

A good-quality dataset of geophysical well logs from Zar-3 is available and can serve for the baseline. The applicability of well logging for monitoring in further phases is also

⁸ <https://ieaghg.org/ccs-resources/monitoring-selection-tool>

supported by the fact that there are open hole intervals available in most of the existing wells. In addition to the “classical” logging methods described above, it is also suggested to consider utilization of the pulsed neutron capture (PNC) logging. The method has brought interesting results for monitoring and modelling of CO₂ behavior in carbonates at the Niagaran pinnacle reefs (Conner et al., 2017). It may be useful for the Zar-3 site as it can distinguish relatively small amounts of injected CO₂.

3.4.3 Tracers

Tracers are according to the IEAGHG tool characterized as: *fluids with a distinct chemical property that provide a unique fingerprint for the injected CO₂. A range of natural and artificial tracers are available to provide information about the transport and dispersion of the injected CO₂. There are two main objectives for using tracers for CO₂ storage site monitoring:*

a) To assess and confirm the migration and behavior of CO₂ in the reservoir; this can be useful for “plume tracking”, understanding fluid pathways and also to help determine the fate of the CO₂ in the reservoir (mineral reactions, residual trapping, dissolution etc). This relies on one or more monitoring boreholes (e.g. production wells in a depleted hydrocarbon reservoir).

b) To aid in the detection or verification of any leakage from the storage reservoir (e.g. through over- / underburden fluid sampling or more often, surface assurance monitoring). It may be possible to estimate the volume and the flow rate of CO₂ leakage if the volume and flow rate of tracer leakage can be measured, assuming even mixing of the tracer with the CO₂ plume and no tracer-CO₂ partitioning (which may not be the case).

In both cases, the tracer allows the injected CO₂ to be distinguished from other “background” sources of CO₂ and may potentially distinguish between CO₂ originating from adjacent storage sites. This will become important if it proves necessary to refute leakage allegations.

Selection of the most suitable tracer(s) for monitoring of CO₂ storage at Zar-3 can be based on report R5.2 Report and dataset: Chemistry of fluids (Franců et al., 2023). Monitoring of the carbon and oxygen isotopic composition of injected and baseline CO₂ may be useful.

4 OPERATIONAL MONITORING

4.1 Mandatory monitoring items

According to the EU CCS Directive as well as the Storage Act that represents the transposition of the EU CCS Directive in the Czech national jurisdiction, the Storage site monitoring plan shall in any case include continuous or intermittent monitoring of the following items:

- a) fugitive emissions of CO₂ at the injection facility,
- b) CO₂ volumetric flow at injection wellheads,

- c) CO₂ pressure and temperature at injection wellheads to determine mass flow,
- d) chemical analysis of the injected material,
- e) reservoir temperature and pressure (PT) to determine CO₂ phase behavior and state.

4.1.1 Fugitive emissions of CO₂ at the injection facility

The infrared (IR) cameras are proposed to mandatory monitoring of the fugitive emissions of CO₂ at the injection facility (Fig. 4-1). IR cameras are provided in both stationary and handheld options. Appropriately placed stationary cameras could provide continuous (24/7) site monitoring. The number of stationary cameras will be adjusted to site dimensions and injection device composition. Furthermore, the automatic evaluation of images or videos from cameras by software with implemented artificial intelligence to detect leaks, enabling the site to be less dependent on human operators, are being developed. Those IR cameras may be available in next few years. The stationary cameras are planned to be chosen in accordance with operator company rules with focus on technical specifications and maintenance cost / available budget.

Fig. 4-1: Monitoring of fugitive emissions from the facility (left), IR handheld camera suitable for such monitoring in detail (right).

Stationary IR cameras are excellent for site monitoring, however for more accurate localizing a handheld camera must be used. Handheld cameras can also detect smaller leaks than stationary cameras. Opgal Ltd. and Teledyne FLIR LLC are two manufacturers with handheld IR camera for CO₂ detection suitable for leak monitoring from individual parts of the injection facility technology. Both cameras can be equipped with quantification software, if necessary, and are ATEX certified. Because of these reasons, the usage of such devices is preferred and strongly recommended.

Leak monitoring using handheld camera should be performed according to schedule consisting of list of individual technology parts, measurement rate and type of process running during detection. Also any irregular, non-standard or ad-hoc process should be monitored with handheld camera.

Acoustic cameras provide a supplementary method to the IR handheld cameras. Acoustic cameras are producing acoustic images that visually display ultrasonic information. Acoustic images are then overlaid in real time on a picture from digital camera. They are also suitable for use in loud, industrial environments. Acoustic cameras are cheaper options for CO₂ leak detection. Their disadvantages are that they hear only pressurized leaks so they cannot be used with all types of considered CCS technologies and they can neither identify nor select specific gases.

Implementation of CO₂ sensors are recommended for fugitive emissions monitoring and for minimizing the safety hazard conditions. Recommended probes for soil gas monitoring can also be used to monitor leaks from underground parts of injection facility. Mentioned probes should be placed in the vicinity of underground devices. Evenly distributed fixed gas detectors should be used for above-ground parts of the technology, including installation in every indoor space. Portable CO₂ detectors for operating personnel are strongly recommended as well. They not only reduce safety hazard risks but help with locating gas leaks missed with above-mentioned detectors.

Proposed frequency of monitoring depends on the method used. Handheld cameras (IR and/or acoustic) monitoring should be done at least once a month at every part of the injection facility. As for the sensors, hourly data collection is proposed, if connected online. If not, data should be measured every hour and collected and evaluated monthly. Workers have to wear CO₂ detectors or at least have in their vicinity whole time during the stay on the site.

During CCS project preparation phase, assessment of estimated potential emissions can be done. Estimated emission from the potential sources could be calculated using adjusted emission factors (Campbell et al., 2021). Estimation could provide necessary information important for sensors layout and cameras monitoring frequency.

4.1.2 CO₂ volumetric flow at injection wellheads and CO₂ pressure and temperature at injection wellheads to determine mass flow

To inject the fluid (CO₂) from storage tanks into the well and control the injection rate and pressure, a surface setup has to be designed. Currently, the option of injecting CO₂ in a supercritical state is considered, and the measuring line and connection to the well need to comply with the purpose. Each of the injectors has to be equipped with a suitable flowmeter for mass flow measurements to measure fluids volumetric properties (supercritical CO₂ expected).

Pressure and temperature (P&T) gauges have to be installed along the injection line on each of critical points with differential pressure transmitter as well as a safety valves and other necessary elements for long term safety operation. At this basis, the mass flow is planned to be determined.

The following design of well monitoring and well surveillance system equipment for the CO₂ injection borehole is suggested at the Zar-3 site (R7.6 Data set and report with results of reservoir containment monitoring; Shchipanov & Pagáč, 2024):

- A flow-meter to be installed permanently at the wellhead to monitor and collect CO₂ injection rate data in real time with minimum sampling rate of 5 seconds.
- Combined wellhead and downhole P&T gauges should be permanently installed in the well to collect measurements with same minimum frequency (5 seconds). The best location of the permanent downhole gauge (PDG) is as close as possible to the reservoir-face.

The minimum requirements for the P&T gauges to be installed at wellhead and downhole of the well are listed in Tab. 4-1.

Table 4-1. Minimum requirements for P&T gauges.

Gauge specification	Value
Pressure accuracy, bar	±0.3
Pressure resolution, bar	0.001
Temperature accuracy, °C	±0.5
Temperature resolution, °C	0.01

This borehole monitoring design will enable:

- Monitoring of wellhead and downhole CO₂ injection rates (see also below), where the latter is calculated based on the surface rate and temperature and pressure downhole (from PDG measurements). The CO₂ injection rate at the reservoir conditions is crucial input data for the interpretation of pressure transient data.
- High frequency of pressure and rate measurements enables monitoring of dynamic process in the near wellbore area such as opening the natural fractures and creating the induced fractures. Here, high-frequency PDG data also allow for distinguishing the wellbore storage effects occurring at the CO₂ injection and masking the early time response in pressure transients.

4.1.3 Chemical analysis of the injected material

Analysis of the injected material/medium is required, which consists of mainly CO₂ and other compounds, such as N₂, Ar, H₂, CH₄, O₂, H₂S, NH₃, CO, SO_x, NO_x and H₂O. Appropriate technique for such analysis is gas chromatography (GC) method (Fig. 4-2), where mixed solution sample is injected into the GC system, sample is vaporized and then carried by carrier gas on the columns, where the mixture is separated into the various components. The amount of each compound is then measured by the detectors, which vary for different analytes.

Applicable for GC system that can measure mentioned analytes is the use of combinations of TCD, FID, PDD, PDHID and NCD detectors. TCD is thermal conductivity detector suitable for analysis of permanent gases (Ar, O₂, N₂, H₂, CO₂, H₂O, SO_x). FID is used for hydrocarbon gases. PDD is pulse discharge detector for NH₃ analysis. PDHID (pulse discharge helium ionization detector) is general purpose detector that can detect various gases in ppb concentrations. NCD is nitrogen chemiluminescence detector also suitable for NH₃, but its primary function is to analyse NO_x.

For analysis of CO₂ gas mixture determined for CCS project, the GC system equipped with TCD, NCD and PDHID detectors is recommended. Analysis can be conducted online on the site or offline in laboratory. On site measurements require use of process gas chromatographs and measurement can be carried out every 15 minutes in case of continual medium injection. Offline measurements can be carried out on laboratory gas chromatograph, for this case, the weekly analysis is proposed.

Based on the state of aggregation of injected mixture, chosen GC system (process and/or laboratory) should be equipped with vaporiser, especially for liquid form of CO₂ mixture. Sampling point whether for process or laboratory GC should be located near the injection well.

Fig. 4-2: Laboratory gas chromatograph suitable for chemical analysis of the injected material.

4.1.4 Reservoir P&T to determine CO₂ phase behavior and state

Regular monitoring and inspection of the underground CO₂ storage facilities is one of the basic duties of every operator of such facility. It is a process that takes place all year round and is necessary for the safe and economical operation of an underground CO₂ storage facility.

The measurement of reservoir P&T is possible to be carried out by installing a PDG with memory, suspended on a wire (wireline / slickline), into the desired depth of the

injection (perforation or open hole interval). The pressure value is considered adequate after approx. 15 min. of stabilization after pulling out the pressure gauge and synchronization data with velocity information record. The result is the course of pressure, in different environments (gas, liquid, or oil). According to the gradient change, the interface between the individual phases will be subsequently determined.

Echo-meter measurement of liquid level in well annulus is suitable for monitoring well in aquifer as well. Together with P&T well-head data (see above), the monitoring will provide all information for reservoir pressure calculations.

Regularly monitoring of reservoir P&T will be carried out on actual monitoring wells and will be enhanced to other re-completed wells in reservoir during the CO₂ storage period.

4.2 Methods of baseline monitoring

It is strongly recommended to continue in all of the baseline monitoring (atmogeochemical, seismological and shallow groundwater monitoring) performed during the CO₂-SPICER project (see chapter 3. Baseline monitoring).

Data provided in the reports R7.3 Data set and Technical Report on atmogeochemical monitoring results (Jirman et al., 2023), R7.5 Data set and report with results of shallow groundwater monitoring (Havlín et al., 2023) and R7.7 Data set and report with results of seismologic monitoring (Jechumtálová & Kolář, 2024) may serve as a baseline reference observed prior to the CO₂ injection.

4.2.1 Atmogeochemical monitoring

Both periodical and continuous soil gas monitoring is proposed to be performed in the same way as during the pre-injection phase. Original monitoring timing and grid is recommended as well to more precise comparison of both archival and future results (see chapter 3.1 Atmogeochemical monitoring). For the original datasets, coordinates of the monitoring points and land use, see R7.3 Data set and Technical Report on atmogeochemical monitoring results (Jirman et al., 2023).

Periodical soil gas monitoring may be performed using a portable Ecoprobe-5TM instrument (RS Dynamics) with 4 infra-red detectors with independent channels for selective analyses of carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), total petroleum (TP = CH₄ to C₄H₁₀) and oxygen (O₂). The same monitoring equipment was used during the baseline monitoring. The permanent probes with independent channels for CO₂ and CH₄ are recommended for the continuous monitoring. Additionally, the carbon isotopic composition of CO₂ and CH₄ in soil gas, e.g. using the isotope ratio mass spectrometry (IRMS), is strongly recommended.

Proposed monitoring has to be supplemented by meteorological data, such as temperature (°C), relative humidity (%) and atmospheric pressure (hPa). Table 4-2 shows baseline CO₂ (%_{vol}) in soil gas in different seasons of the year.

Tab. 4-2: CO₂ (%vol) in soil gas measured during the baseline monitoring: range is given as numerator, averages as denominator. Dataset based on the 8 monitoring campaigns; 95 monitoring points each.

Spring	Summer-autumn	Winter
<u>0.07 – 9.09</u>	<u>0.06 – 9.67</u>	<u>0.04 – 2.33</u>
1.20	1.66	0.32

Additional method recommended for the Zar-3 site is flux monitoring chamber technique, which measures CO₂ emissions quantitatively from the soil to the atmosphere. The method is used for evaluation of gas leakage from the poorly abandoned wells (Jirman et al. 2023).

4.2.2 Seismological monitoring

The configuration and extension of future seismic monitoring network will depend on the detailed specifications required as an output from the seismological monitoring. In general, two options are possible: (1) to monitor seismic activity (if any) at the site and its closer vicinity, or (2) to obtain additional information about sources of activity. These would include information about source orientation (expressed e.g. as source moment tensor) or cracks opening and their spreading. In the former case a network of about 5 stations⁹ is sufficient; in the latter, the network of 10 or more stations¹⁰ is needed.

On the base of the facts given above it is proposed to install a seismic network of at least 5 stations in the Zar-3 area during the operational phase. The configuration of the seismological monitoring network should be the same or similar as in pre-injection (baseline) phase (see chapter 3.2 Seismological monitoring); the characteristic network diameter should be 2-5 km. It is desirable from both the security and scientific points to extend this network up to 10 or more stations at least in the critical phases of CO₂ injection (e.g. beginning of the injection). The network will monitor possible local natural events, anthropogenic activity nearby and brittle fracturing in the storage, if any.

Deployment of the seismic monitoring stations into a borehole with depth of first tens of meters does not improve signal to noise ratio significantly taking into account increased costs of station deployment due to the borehole drilling. On the other hand, there is no doubt, that shallow burial of stations (first decimeters or meters) can significantly eliminate some types of noise (e.g. that caused by wind). The other types of artificial noise can be often eliminated by careful selection of a station site. We therefore recommend short testing measurement (e.g. one or several days) on the proposed site before final station deployment.

⁹ A seismic event location is 4 parameters problem (3 spatial and 1 time coordinates have to be determined). Five station offers (in an ideal case) five data items for P wave onsets and five data items for S wave onsets; however, the ideal amount of data could not be guaranteed for every event, therefore we consider 5 stations network as a reasonable minimum for location task.

¹⁰ The source Moment Tensor (MT), which describe seismic source orientation, has 6 parameters. As usage of S waves for MT determination is problematic, the reasonable minimum observations is 10 or more in this case.

4.2.3 Shallow groundwater monitoring

The shallow groundwater monitoring is strongly recommended. Most of the original monitoring objects/points of the baseline monitoring can be used as well for future geochemical sampling campaigns (see chapter 3.3 Shallow groundwater monitoring). For the original datasets of the baseline monitoring, see R7.5 Data set and report with results of shallow groundwater monitoring (Havlín et al., 2023). For the future monitoring, it is recommended to measure the following parameters: groundwater level, spring yield, electrical conductivity, alkalinity, pH, water temperature, major and minor elements and dissolved gasses. The original monitoring network may be broadened by several existing / newly drilled monitoring wells.

4.3 Seismic monitoring

Seismic monitoring plays an important role in the carbon dioxide storage projects as it provides good spatial resolution and is sensitive to changes in pore fluid (Lumley 2010). It can be applied for both conformance and assurance monitoring. Conformance monitoring is broadly defined as a possibility of tracking the propagation of the plume inside the primary containment to confirm its' behavior matches the project goals. Assurance monitoring means the possibility of detecting various adverse effects, such as CO₂ leakage outside of the containment or excessive induced seismicity.

4.3.1 Experiences of the seismic monitoring

Seismic monitoring can be conducted using several different approaches. Active surface 4D (time-lapse 3D) seismic provides the full 3D image of the evolving plume and potentially detect leakages. It was successfully applied in a number of commercial (Phythian et al. 2023, Eiken et al. 2011) and demonstration or research projects, such as the CO₂CRC Otway project (Pevzner et al. 2017), Ketzin (Ivandic et al. 2015). The utilisation of the permanent receiver arrays allows for a considerable reduction in the degree of invasiveness and improvement of repeatability of the surveys (Jervis et al. 2018, Pevzner et al. 2017).

Downhole seismic uses several different acquisition techniques. Conventional offset VSP geometry was reported to be useful for both detection of the plume (Tertyshnikov et al. 2017) and detailed evaluation of the changes of elastic properties through FWI (Egorov et al. 2017) or other techniques (Al Hosni et al. 2016). Walk away and 4D VSP were deployed to monitor CO₂ injection in a number of projects, including Aquistor (Harris 2017, White et al. 2019), Otway (Yurikov et al. 2022, AlNasser et al. 2017), Decatur (Couëslan et al. 2014), CSIRO In-Situ lab (Michael et al. 2020), CaMI (Lawton et al. 2017) and other projects. Note that both conventional geophones and fibre optic cables via distributed acoustic sensing technology (DAS, enables continuous, real-time measurements along the entire length of a fibre optic cable) were successfully used for these purposes.

Application cross-hole seismic technology was reported for Cranfield (Ajo-Franklin et al. 2013), Nagaoka (Saito et al. 2006) and other projects, including cases where it was used to monitor CO₂ injection in one of the reef formations (Gupta et al. 2020).

4.3.2 Feasibility study for Zar-3 site

To be able to assess the applicability of different type of seismic survey as described above and to select the most suitable one for our pilot storage site Zar-3, the feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods (hereinafter referred to as the Study) was performed. The Study was added to the project outputs as result R7.8 “Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ plume monitoring” (Pevzner, Gurevich 2023). In accordance with project documentations, the Study was subcontracted.

The Study aimed to evaluate the detectability of CO₂ in the Zar-3 site (mature hydrocarbon field) in the reservoir using active time-lapse seismic surveys. Study was focused on conformance monitoring scenarios only and does not consider leakage of the CO₂ outside of the reservoir. To achieve this, the Study performed a desktop study based on a combination of flow simulations, rock physics and seismic modelling.

The general workflow includes the following steps:

- Initially, the Study analyzed the likely plume geometry from the flow simulations
- The Study identified the location for a synthetic well to perform rock physics modelling
- The results of the rock physics modelling was used to generate a series of elastic models, which were utilized for 1.5D modelling.

The specifics of the Zar-3 site is in the fact that it is an oil and gas field, where carbonate rocks form reservoir and the injection of CO₂ will coincide with this hydrocarbon production.

The Study simulated seismic response on the grid of seismic sources and receivers, which would be suitable for evaluating surface and downhole geometry. Then, the Study performed time-lapse data analysis to evaluate the level of time-lapse data and decide on the detectability of the plume using different acquisition geometries based on the previous experience with the repeatability of each method.

Based on dynamic modelling and simulation (WP3, result V2), geometry of the plume was defined, using the following criteria:

- Initially, the cell would have less than 2% of free gas
- CO₂ saturation is greater than 10%
- 70,000 tones of CO₂ will have been injected at the end of the injection.

The plume is increasing from ~100 x 100 m in three months from the start of the injection to 200 x 400 m in size at the end of the injection. Plume thickness can reach up to 35 m (away from the injector – the ZA7 well). The size of the plume with significant thickness (>10-15 m) does not exceed 200 x 200 m. For these CO₂ plume dimensions, the

seismic simulations for different seismic surveys (surface, borehole) has been worked out.

The Study used MIT OASES software to perform the simulations, which allows for realistic simulations, including a full range of multiples, but restricts to the 1D model of elastic properties. To perform the simulations, the log data (including the results of rock physics modelling) have been down-sampled to form 2 m thick layers using Backus averaging (Backus 1962).

Seismic simulation was focused on both surface seismic and borehole seismic. As surface seismic, 3D seismic was simulated and tested.

Borehole seismic was represented by different versions of vertical seismic profiling (VSP), i.e. VSP with zero offset (standard) and with offset geometry, walk-away VSP geometry, time-laps (4D) VSP; all with standard geophones or DAS receivers (see Fig. 4-3).

Fig. 4-3: Different geometry of VSP – standard, deviated, offset and walkaway.

Cross-hole seismic was also simulated; one of the main limitations of the cross-hole seismic is the limited power of the downhole seismic sources. As such, this technique might be suitable in cases where the distance between the pairs of wells that can be used to deploy seismic sources and receivers should be limited. Fortunately, the portion of the Zar-3 site planned for CO₂ storage is relatively small, with the plume size not exceeding ~300 x 600 m with a number of relatively vertical wells with limited offsets from each other.

4.3.3 Recommendations for the seismic monitoring at Zar-3

The recommendations for seismic monitoring at the Zar-3 site were derived from the subcontracted result – R7.8 “Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ plume monitoring” (Pevzner, Gurevich 2023) and include the following:

- surface seismic monitoring of the CO₂ injection into the depleted oil and gas reservoir has limited chances of imaging the plume because of the small time-lapse signal level;
- borehole seismic is likely to be useful in detecting and imaging the plume (because of the higher degree of repeatability); DAS receivers are the preferred option;
- a combination of offset VSPs (potentially with permanent sources) and 4D VSP are the preferred set of geometries;
- application of cross-hole time-lapse seismic technique is feasible. However, the main motivation to use it is likely related to the imaging of the plume using reflected waves rather than travel time tomography.

Based on the above conclusions, we suggest in our Site monitoring plan for seismic monitoring to use 4D (time-lapse) VSP with offset geometry and with permanent DAS receivers. From existing wells, located in Zar-3 site, we plan to use mainly vertical wells and/or moderately deviated wells, i.e. ZA3, ZA4A and ZA6A. Well ZA7 is considered as injection well; in case that new injection well would be drilled, the well ZA7 could be used for VSP measurement. Utilization of horizontal wells (ZA5H, ZA8AH, ZA9AH, ZA14H) for VSP is limited, mainly due to technical issues with receiver’s installation.

4.4 Monitoring wells

Currently, the operational wells provide possibility to use them for monitoring purposes in future. The ZA3, ZA5H (Fig. 4-4), ZA6a and ZA8 are among the most prospective. New perforations may be necessary to hit the following monitoring target places:

- aquifer underlying the residual oil zone, where the CO₂ flow should be traced;
- aquifer part further away from the injection point and closer to the spill points to acquire signals soon enough, that the CO₂ plume is approaching the spill point, so that action can be taken to prevent CO₂ escaping from the storage complex through the spill point;
- overburden seal horizons in the Mikulov, Nesvačilka and Němčice Fms., best in places with relatively higher porosity and permeability;
- adjacent seal horizons at similar depth as the stored CO₂ to monitor eventual horizontal escape of CO₂ from the storage complex.

Possible use of wells for monitoring purposes is shown in Fig. 4-4, 4-5 and 4-6.

Fig. 4-4: Sketch of CO₂ storage complex with carbonate reservoir and three seal horizons: In – injection well, M – monitoring wells, W – ground water wells, SP – spill point, house – villages, contour lines – soil gas composition maps with CO₂ levels measured at least 3 times a year and compared with the base line (pre-storage) maps.

The monitoring is recommended to use the following equipment to register specific parameters:

- pressure gauges to monitor changes in the formation fluid pressure;
- thermometers to follow cooling and heating of the system associated with injections and periods between injections due to thermal relaxation of the rock system;
- optical fibers to monitor the entire temperature profile;
- gamma-gamma, neutron-gamma and neutron-neutron well logging to monitor changes in depth of the gas/oil and oil/water contacts;

Fig. 4-5: ZA5H well profile with the well logs.

Fig. 4-6: Current ZA5H well design with recommended monitoring perforations, either in Némčice or in Mikulov fms. The deeper part of the well must be isolated using a cement plug.

4.5 Fit-for-purpose model for studying well monitoring capabilities

A fit-for-purpose reservoir model (for more details, see R7.6 Data set and report with results of reservoir containment monitoring by Shchipanov & Pagáč, 2024) was assembled in the Saphir software based on the basic geological data including the reservoir geometry, well location and average reservoir (such as porosity and pay-thickness at the well location, pore volume compressibility) and fluid (brine PVT) properties.

The main purposes for assembling and using the reservoir model are:

- interpretation and matching the well testing results to estimate reservoir properties and boundary conditions in the well drainage area as far as may be evaluated from available pressure transient data;
- designing and simulating well tests for detecting the natural fracture openings;
- evaluation feasibility of detecting and monitoring natural fracture opening for water and CO₂ injection.

The simulations assumed that the variation in the reservoir depth, pay thickness, presence of remaining oil and gas in the reservoir as well as impact of pressure support from a limited aquifer connected from the East did not play a significant role in the model. The reservoir model and the ZA-7 well completion schematics are illustrated in Fig. 4-7. The well has 112 m of open-hole connection to the reservoir of total thickness of 158 m providing limited entry well-reservoir connection (Bourdet, 2002).

Fig. 4-7: A reservoir segment model containing a vertical water injection well in focus (left) and the well completion schematics showing open-hole interval and initial water saturation profile (right).

A water injection well test was carried out after the ZA7 well completion in 2004, where downhole pressure gauge was installed and provided 10-hour pressure measurements during well shut-in (Fig. 4-8). Water was injected for 5.5 hours with two

rate measurements, where the first hour of the injection the wellbore was filled in by the injected water with well injection at atmospheric pressure at the wellhead. Large changing wellbore storage was observed in combination with large well skin factor interpreted at the beginning of the shut-in period (Fig. 4-8). The large skin (providing additional pressure drop of 71 bar (Fig. 4-8, left) in comparison with 4 bar overall pressure drop ignoring the skin (Fig. 4-8, right) seems to be related to the damage (clogging) of the near wellbore area with drilling mud, since it's far above a skin provided by the limited entry connection (Fig. 4-8, right).

Fig. 4-8: Pressure fall-off response and its Bourdet derivative from water injection test (crosses / dots) and matching the response with the segment reservoir model with large (left) and zero (right) well skin – red and black lines. Flow regimes: identified in the real response derivative (left) and in the simulated response with zero skin (right).

Interpretation of the pressure fall-off response and its Bourdet derivative in the log-log scale allowed to separate four flow regimes (Fig. 4-8, left): (1) wellbore storage effect at early time (0-0.3 hr), (2) limited well entry response (0.3-0.7 hr), (3) radial flow regime (0.7-2 hr) and (4) boundary-dominated flow regime at the late time (2-10 hr). The last flow regime is governed by the closest no-flow reservoir boundaries to the West and South from the well (Fig. 4-7, left). It is assumed that the near wellbore area has been successfully cleaned-up during periodical water injection during twenty years. A zero-skin case was then simulated on with the same well-reservoir model to get base-line pressure transient response for the well (Fig. 4-8, right).

The geomechanical study (Nermoen et al, 2024) as resulted in the safe injection envelope showing fracture opening pressure for natural fractures, induced fracturing pressure and pressure at which fault reactivation may happen (Fig. 4-9, left). Fixing reservoir temperature at 15 °C (the minimum temperature of injected CO₂), the fracture opening and induced fracturing pressures may be evaluated as 224 and 267 bar correspondingly. An exponential increase of the effective reservoir permeability may be modelled in this range to model opening of natural fractures (Fig. 4-9, right). Such fracture modelling approach seems to be sufficient for the purposes of the feasibility study. Injection of water and CO₂ may be further simulated on the reservoir model matched to the well test results.

Fig. 4-9: Safe injection envelope from (Nermoen et al., 2024) indicating fracture opening and induced fracturing pressures at 224 and 267 bar for reservoir temperature of 15 °C (left) and pressure dependent multipliers for reservoir porosity and permeability (right). Two permeability multipliers: without and with natural fracture opening contributions. SRT range is the pressure build-up expected in the step rate test designs.

4.6 Well testing to study opening of natural fractures

The geomechanical evaluations (Nermoen et al., 2024) have revealed large uncertainties with in-situ stresses which made also uncertain the assessment of horizontal stresses governing opening and closure of the natural fracture networks during reservoir pressure build-up and drawdown. Such dynamic fracture behavior may also be evaluated from dynamic data analysis presented above, although no reservoir permeability changes were revealed, probably due to narrow pressure range associated with the field data available. The geomechanical study (Nermoen et al. 2024) has however provided a prediction of potential opening of the natural fractures (Fig. 4-9) under the uncertainty described above and suggested a description of the pressure dependent fracture permeability (Fig. 4-9).

Step-rate testing (Shchipanov et al. 2017) or step-rate injection may be used for detecting and monitoring of opening / closure of natural fractures under reservoir pressure changes if PDG is installed in the well monitored. A step-rate test with water injection is recommended in the well in focus (ZA-7) before CO₂ pilot to reduce the uncertainties with the geomechanical parameters described above.

The scope and objectives of such step-rate well test may include:

- Since the well ZA-7 was recently recompleted with wellbore cleaning and new tubing installed, the current well-reservoir parameters may be evaluated from the well test including reservoir flow capacity (permeability-thickness product), well skin and wellbore friction (from combined wellhead and downhole pressure measurements). Both pressure transients from injection and shut-in periods may be analyzed for this purpose.

- Opening of natural fractures as predicted by the geomechanical evaluations may be studied from the step-rate test employing the approach suggested in (Shchipanov et al., 2017).

Following these objectives, a step-rate test was designed based on the knowledge obtained and the well-reservoir model matched in the previous well test (from 2004) analysis described in the previous section (Fig. 4-8, right). Since the well was recompleted, zero skin model (Fig. 4-8, right) was used in combination with the pressure dependent reservoir permeability (Fig. 4-9, right). The SRT design includes three injection steps (3-hour duration) with following measurement of pressure fall-off during the well shut-in (at least 9 hours). Two scenarios were simulated: without and with fracture opening at 224 bar (Fig. 4-10, left). Both analysis of the simulated SRT results in linear scale (Fig. 4-10, left) and log-log scale (Fig. 4-10, right), where pressure transient responses and their derivative to injection steps is analysed, provided clear indication of the fracture opening. This indication consists of much lower pressure drop and drifting-down of pressure and derivative at the third step, where fractures start to open.

Fig. 4-10: Step rate test simulated for water injection (left) and pressure transient responses and their derivatives for three steps of the test in log-log plot (right). Crosses in right part correspond to the 'Fracture closed' case, while lines with the same colour for the same steps to the 'Fracture opening' case.

The simulations have confirmed that SRT with water injection may serve as reliable tool for detection and studying fracture opening. This simulation study did not account for potential induced fracturing, since opening of natural fractures is expected as the first event happening at injection and pressure build-up. Studying this effect is therefore giving priority. At the same time, induced fracturing may also be detected with SRT, which may be a subject for further study of the reservoir in focus.

4.7 Well testing and injection monitoring during CO₂ injection

The SRT with water injection simulated in the previous section may be extended to the case of CO₂ injection and used as the well control framework for further time-lapse monitoring of the well. The short steps with increasing rate in SRT may be substituted

with longer steps of combined increasing and decreasing rates in long-term time-lapse well monitoring.

Fig. 4-11 illustrates simulation results for similar SRT to one simulated in the previous section for water injection and shown in Fig. 4-10 (left), where the injectant is changed from water to CO₂. As in the water injection scenario above, two cases of pressure dependent fracture permeability are considered (Fig. 4-9): ‘Fracture closed’ and ‘Fracture opening’. Flooding the near wellbore area with CO₂ has an impact on the first injection step (Fig. 4-11, left), where the pressure derivative is significantly affected (Fig. 4-11, right). CO₂ plume in the near wellbore area is stabilized at the second step, providing similar pressure transient responses and derivatives for both fracture cases (transients and derivatives are coinciding in Fig. 4-11 right). In contrast to water injection responses (Fig. 4-10, right), presence of CO₂ plume in the near wellbore area is reflected by lower derivative at the early time (0.001-0.01 hr, Fig. 4-11, right). Fracture opening at the third step may clearly detected at the third step with the derivative shifting down for the whole duration of the response (Fig. 4-11, right).

Fig. 4-11: Similar SRT to one illustrated in Fig. 4-10 for CO₂ injection. Crosses in right part correspond to the ‘Fracture closed’ case, while lines with the same colour for the same steps to the ‘Fracture opening’ case.

The feasibility study has confirmed possibility of detecting fracture opening under CO₂ injection. At the same time, impact of growing CO₂ plume should first be observed in pressure transients to provide baseline for further successful fracture opening detection.

The analysis and evaluation of available dynamic field data have shown that installation of permanent downhole gauge (PDG) in production wells is an effective option for permanent well and reservoir monitoring for the fractured formation in focus. Application of time-lapse PTA in combination with fit-for-purpose reservoir simulations (Shchipanov et al., 2014) allowed for monitoring of well and reservoir parameters. Similar monitoring approach is suggested for the planned CO₂ pilot.

A step-rate well test with water injection is suggested before the CO₂ pilot to study potential opening of natural fractures at injection and reduce the uncertainty with geomechanical parameters, e.g. to evaluate unknown parameters such as minimum horizontal stress.

The feasibility study of step-rate CO₂ injection confirmed that PTA of the step-responses may be used to evaluate CO₂ plume growth in the near wellbore area and to detect opening of natural fractures. Similar approach may be further tested for detection of induced fracturing, which may happen after natural fracture opening as predicted by the geomechanical evaluations. This effect may be addressed in a future study.

4.8 Downhole fluid geochemistry

Prior to the storage, data on oil, gas and formation water chemistry are compiled and used in experiments and modelling of the CO₂-fluid-rock interactions. During the CO₂ storage operations, water sampling through the monitoring wells will be difficult, but gas sampling is recommended. Increasing amount of CO₂ is expected in the monitoring wells through the selected perforations. Even if the CO₂ would be dissolved in the aquifer water, it is very probable, that CO₂ will exsolve from water during the sampling. Tracers may be added to the injected CO₂, but their concentration in the storage volume will be very low (or very expensive) and, hence, not very efficient.

Additional measurements are recommended to be used in the existing shallow hydrogeological wells to monitor signals of changing pH value and CO₂ or HCO₃⁻ in the ground water, for details we refer to the chapter 3.3 of this report.

5 POST-CLOSURE MONITORING

The main aim of the post-closure monitoring is to prove the modelled behavior of the CO₂ and to confirm the CO₂ remains stored permanently with no leakage to the surface. The post-closure monitoring shall be based on the information collected and modelled during the implementation of the monitoring plan as defined in Section (§) 9 of the Storage Act and in point 2 of the Annex to the Storage Act (on updating the monitoring plan). It shall serve in particular to provide information required for the transfer of responsibility to the competent authority as defined in Section (§) 13 of the Storage Act.

For the post-closure monitoring, following methods are recommended to be performed:

- fugitive emissions of CO₂ at the injection facility – to detect possible CO₂ leakage from the injection facility;
- reservoir PT to determine CO₂ phase behavior and state;
- borehole seismic (VSP, cross-hole) + DAS – to monitor the CO₂ plume and to identify potential leakage pathways;
- seismological monitoring – to detect possible induced seismicity related to the Zar-3 storage complex;
- atmogeochemical (soil-gas) monitoring – to detect possible manifestations of CO₂ leakage at the surface and to control environmental impacts and risks;
- shallow groundwater monitoring above the CO₂ storage complex – to control environmental impacts and risks;

- downhole fluid chemistry through selected perforations in the monitoring wells – to provide the evidence of the extent of the CO₂ plume and of no migration of the CO₂ into the overburden seal horizons.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The Site monitoring plan was prepared with respect to the Act No. 85/2012 Sb. on storage of carbon dioxide in natural underground geological formations as one of the main obligations of a storage site operator, both during site operations and after the site closure. The plan involved as an input the international CCS project guidelines (such as the Guidance Documents to the European CCS Directive), other international literature and individual reports of the CO₂-SPICER project.

Following methods were used during the baseline monitoring: atmogeochemical monitoring, seismological monitoring and the shallow groundwater monitoring. Other recommended methods prior to the CO₂ injection include the downhole pressure and temperature monitoring, geophysical logging and, possibly, the fluid tracers.

During the operational monitoring, the following mandatory items have to be monitored: (1) fugitive emissions of CO₂ at the injection facility, (2) CO₂ volumetric flow at injection wellheads, (3) CO₂ pressure and temperature at injection wellheads to determine mass flow, (4) chemical analysis of the injected material and (5) reservoir temperature and pressure to determine CO₂ phase behavior and state.

A design of well monitoring system was suggested for the CO₂ injection well including installation of permanent wellhead pressure and temperature gauges in combination with flow-meter at the wellhead. This will allow the monitoring of the wellbore and the well performance as well as evaluation of the changes in the near wellbore area of the reservoir, which may challenge the reservoir containment of the injected CO₂.

For the post-closure phase, it is strongly recommended to continue using all the monitoring methods applied during the baseline monitoring phase, which include the atmogeochemical, seismological, shallow groundwater monitoring, well logging, borehole seismic (VSP, cross-hole) with the DAS and downhole fluid chemistry.

The summary recommendation of the monitoring methods for the Zar-3 pilot site for all monitoring stages is shown in the following table (Tab. 6.1).

Tab. 6-1: Recommended monitoring methods for the Zar-3 pilot site.

Method	Monitoring stage		
	Baseline (prior injection)	Operational (during injection)	Post-injection (after injection)
Fugitive emissions of CO ₂ at the injection facility	Not possible	+++++ (mandatory)	++++
CO ₂ volumetric flow at injection wellheads	Not possible	+++++ (mandatory)	Not possible
CO ₂ PT at injection wellheads to determine mass flow	Not possible	+++++ (mandatory)	Not possible
Chemical analysis of the injected material	Not possible	+++++ (mandatory)	Not possible
Reservoir PT to determine CO ₂ phase behavior and state	Not possible	+++++ (mandatory)	++++
Surface seismic (3D, multi-component seismic)	Done (archival data)	Not suitable	Not suitable
Well logging	Done (archival data)	+++	++
Borehole seismic (VSP, cross-hole) + DAS	No data	++++	++++
Seismological monitoring	Done	++++	++++
Atmogeochemical (soil-gas) monitoring	Done	++++	++++
Shallow groundwater monitoring	Done	+++	+++
Tracers (gas or volatile liquids)	No data	+	+
Downhole fluid chemistry	Done	++++	++++

**number of crosses: 5 = mandatory, 4 = strongly recommended, 3 = definitely applicable, 2 = probably applicable*

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co2-spicer.geology.cz.

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

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